

Women and Social Media in Evolving Millennium

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Sheela Krishnan

Management Consultant

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Women, usually get married around 20-25 years old and enter new phase of life. Then their priorities changed to husband, career, & children their education and family, and used to be very busy up to 40 -45 years.

By that time 20 -25 years of family life will be over.

Everyone would have got a dream boy but married to an entirely different personality and would have given birth to one or two children in imitation. Even if they are a boy or a girl, now they would be in college days and would have created a circle of friends of their choice and started spending time with them and unavoidable gap is formed between mother and son /daughter.

Now the focus is on children’s education, well being of Self, career and hence couples would be missing the intimate moments. At this time husband concentrate on earnings and children run in search of the career.

Only those mothers are in dangerous, they are lonely at the age of forty plus. No one is there to spend time with her. There is no one to appreciate his cooking or uniqueness. She has lived for her husband and family and now feels a vacuum has been created in her life.

Nature is always great and it will show in her physical and mental health and now she feels the missed out things in life. She would have learnt to use smart phones and social media and would have find out her old friends, formed a group, revived friendship and sharing twenty long years’ stories..... And started using Social Media and in due course of time addicted to it.

Now starts the problem. Friends / groups and of course Unknown people will start following her and when it comes to get connected to unknown people, first choice is to start talking about hobbies with people who are not familiar and then add up to it until late at night. Often women are affected by it, but it is not wrong at any time with familiar friends, but new social networking sites are very dangerous at midnight,

Women should understand that men are usually in the wrong view of Women who are get connected with Unfamiliar men and there is no need to talk to men at midnight without any problems in their family. If someone is comforting, it will be easy for the mind to be clear and understand what the motivator’s motivation is.

It is important to understand that there is no need for a wolf's comfort to say that women who are online at midnight are laughing or laughing. Thousands of wolves are wandering in their trap.

Never let you feel the smile of the uninformed people, do not let others cool in your family's trouble; do not give the devil a place for your privacy. At the same time, your family, your value, keeps your children in mind and Just keep up with it good friends.

Keep in mind that your temporary comfort search should not bump into a permanent family!

Strictly avoid midnight chatting with unknown persons.

Types of Social Media Crime Faced

1. Profile Hacking

Profile hacking happens when, as a user, you are not able to log in to your account. Someone has complete control of your account and has changed all the credentials. Facebook is the most hacked social networking site and it generally happens because of the following reasons:

- Not logging out from the account
- Sharing passwords or having passwords that are easily predicted
- Hacking the email with which you login to your Facebook account
- Logging in through Facebook options for apps

2. Photo Morphing

Photo morphing is a special effect that allows a person to morph or change one image or shape into another without any difficulty. As per the 4th quadrant of 2017, there is roughly around 3.2 Billion images shared every day. It is easy for a hacker to use your images, morph it and then use it for porn sites or blackmailing for financial/sexual gains.

You can't stop anyone from morphing. If your images are publicly available, people can easily access them and make use of them to morph. Every popular male and female celebrity is probably photo-shopped and used by most porn sites to satisfy sexual fantasies. You never know when someone takes your photographs and use them.

3. Offer and Shopping Scams

You would often come across messages, post which would say 'Click on the link to claim the offer' or 'spin the wheel to win.' These offers would generally ask you to forward the message to another 20 people once you have registered in order to get the code or coupon. You won't get coupons but the host would get your personal information.

Tips to follow to be Safe from Offer and Shopping Scams

- The simplest thing to do is to make a quick check of the promotion/deal of the brand or the organization of their social media page/their homepage.
- There are chances were the hacker would have made a fake profile. In such instances check is the site has a secured https://. Also check how well the website is made and if the tone of communication is too sloppy.
- Don't buy fake social media followers as they are more likely to get your credit card details and later use it or ask you to share your id and password to get you genuine followers.
- Do not transfer money or give in card details if the discounts are too-steep, or have poor reviews, or unclear refund policies.
- A lot of people trust offers like shown below and end up shopping and getting no discount.
- Trust your instincts and lodge a complaint if you ever think you are being scammed. But remember, this is the mostly not so entertained complaints of the internet world. So try to be as secure as you can when it comes to online shopping.

4. Romance and Dating Scams

There are people out there who would connect to you on social media, interact with you, and persuade you to move to a different form of communication through various excuses. Once they realize that you are falling for them, they would send you small gifts to show you that it's same on either side. After a point the romantic period would start declining and they would start asking for monetary help in the form of recharge, booking flight tickets to meet and the list only grows.

There are also extreme cases where a guy promises to marry the girl and before the marriage runs away with all her money. It is basically a trick/scam which would begin with romantic intensions to build goodwill and later commit fraud.

The other form of romance scam is where the person who you fall in love with will ask you to strip naked in front of camera. He is more likely to chat with you on Skype and you might be so much in love with the person opposite that you wouldn't mind doing him/her a favour. This is the last time he/ she would chat with you and then you will start receiving blackmail calls.

Many people try to take an offline scam to online where they record videos of girls in compromising positions for porn sites.

Tips to Follow to be Safe from Romance and Dating Scams

- Don't accept friend requests from random people. Don't reply to messages to people who are not in your friend list. Facebook generally warns people when they get messages from people who are not in their friend list. Do not chat with anyone and everyone especially someone you don't know.
- If the fraudster is calling you to some place, alone to give you something or asking you to go on a date then don't go.
- Don't transfer your card or bank details with anybody at any cost. If somebody is threatening you, report about it to the police.
- Don't strip or send your nudes through digital.

5. Link Baiting

Link bait happens when the content of your website or pages gets linked to other sites because they want to and not because they have asked you. A few instances where link bait has been showcased are-

- Your photo just got leaked on internet, check here:
- Look what people are talking about you:
- This video of yours is going viral. To know more click here:

When clicking on any of these links, there are chances where you are likely to send the same message to the people from your profile. This link would be sent from your name and would make people think that you are the one doing it.

6. Information Theft

Informational theft occurs when an imposter identifies key pieces of personally identifiable information like social security, driving license number in order to impersonate someone else. Many people tend to store passwords or bank details on their email. Many people try to have very private conversation on Facebook or Instagram messengers. Businesswomen are also more likely to be at the risk of information theft especially with respect to her organization.

Women bloggers these days are faced by plagiarism of various types. When they try to open their business page on Facebook for the first time, there are chances that their competitors would already have promoted bad things to bring down their reputation.

Tips to follow to be safe from Information Theft

- If you have a name which is common differentiate it with something that people know would connect to your business..
- It is possible to merge pages on Facebook, so you can merge the fake page with yours and claim that you are the official owner of the page.
- Ensure that you don't store credit card details and crucial passwords on Social Media messengers too.
- When you use email extensions on chrome, beware they are genuine one as they are reading through your emails and have access to all the data.

7. Cyber Bullying

Posting any kind of humiliating content on the social media or sending vulgar messages online, or threatening to commit any act of violence, or stalking by means of calls, messages or threatening of child pornography is called as cyber bullying. There are many Indian laws that can allow a woman to deal with this and with the help of Indian Police, you can sort this particular issue.

Tips to Follow to Stay Safe From Cyber Bullying

- Approach the police when you are getting harassed online.
- Do not sit idle as that would only make the bully think that you are scared and won't be of any harm to them.

Here is Where You Can Know Some of Our Cyber Laws

- <https://www.cybercrimecomplaints.com/cyber-crime-cells-india>
- <http://www.cybervictims.org/index.html> (NGO)

These are the crucial factors with respect to cyber crimes that happen in India.

Please keep tabs on the kind of people you befriend on social media and also always have a check on your privacy.

Even in the friends group also, people across globe are also connected and due to different time zone they are chatting at late nights. Different kind of people, different culture, different life style are being exhibited in groups and thus developing a peer pressure. Mind just started comparing with everyone and results in feeling inferior. Even this is also creating misunderstanding between couples.

At the same time, however close a friend may be, don't share details about husband and wife issues or give space to any man /woman to interfere into your family life. In today's scenario social gathering / get together/ dining out with family friends and groups are creating hell a lot of problems in life and resulting in legal separation in family.

Now this is used as a tool for religious conversion also.

Women, as usual have to be Multi tasking, independent and courageous enough to face the challenges, on her way to Success.

Never tell people more than what they need to know!

Be Safe Than Being Sorry.

References

1. <https://www.cybercrimecomplaints.com/cyber-crime-cells-india>
2. <http://www.cybervictims.org/index.html> (NGO)
3. <https://www.soravjain.com/cyber-security-for-women-in-social-media>